

Research on the Connection Between the Administrative Capacity of the National Education System and the Management of Educational Change (Part Two)

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ABSTRACT: Changes and challenges in the universal social system are also leading to obvious changes in education systems. In this context, there is a need for efficiency among national education systems, made possible by developing administrative capacity and accelerating educational change. Starting from this premise, the present article reflects a scientific approach based on the quantitative research method in order to establish the connection between the administrative capacity of the Romanian education system and the management of educational change. Thus, the phenomenon of change plays a fundamental role in the process of evolution of educational management, as educational entities become organizations in terms of structure, management, vision, mission, relationships and climate. Organizational development and good governance are therefore supported by effective management of administrative capacity in line with educational change.

KEYWORDS: administrative capacity, impact, institutional accountability, determinants of effective educational change management, responsibility

The second part of the research continues the scientific approach through which the hypothesis is validated that between administrative capacity and educational change management there is a connection possible only through a process focused on educational infrastructure development, good management and flexibility to change. In the following the means that establish the synergy of good administration-management-adaptation are presented. Specific elements are highlighted to ensure the link between administrative capacity and the management of educational provision: adaptation to change followed by a strategy of innovation supported by the benchmarks of institutional responsibility and accountability, cohesion between educational provision and the labor market, transparency and institutional integrity. Based on a new set of 12 questions, the research contributes significantly to the connection between administrative capacity and educational change management, and to the identification of educational change management priorities for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the national education system. Following part one of this paper, part two will begin with question 13.

13. Are you satisfied with the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing?

Out of the survey respondents, 19.5% of survey participants are very satisfied with the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing, while 39.1% are very satisfied with the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing. The remaining 41.5% have a neutral opinion on this issue.

Table no. 33. Are you satisfied with the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing?

		Frequency	Percent
Validated date	very small extent	7	17.1
	small extent	9	22.0
	neither small nor large	17	41.5
	largely	6	14.6
	to a very large extent	2	4.9
	Total	41	100.0

People working in the private sector have a negative or at most neutral opinion about the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing, while among people working in the public sector opinions are more diverse: 36.1% have a negative opinion, 41.7% have a neutral opinion and 22.3% have a positive opinion, i.e. they are satisfied or very satisfied with the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing.

Cross tab no. 37. Area of professional activity* Are you satisfied with the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing?

			to a very small extent	to a small extent	neither small nor large	largely	to a very large extent
Your area of professional activity:	Public	Frequency	4	9	15	6	2
		%	11.1%	25.0%	41.7%	16.7%	5.6%
	Privat	Frequency	3	0	2	0	0
		%	60.0%	0.0%	40.0%	0.0%	0.0%

$\chi^2=8,510$; $df=4$; $p=0,075$

In the following table, the frequencies and weights of respondents' answers on their satisfaction with the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing can be followed by age. While younger people are more neutral, as they get older the proportion of those who have a negative opinion of the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing increases.

Cross tab no. 38. Age* Are you satisfied with the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing?

			to a very small extent	to a small extent	neither small nor large	largely	to a very large extent
Age	31-40 years old	Frequency	0	3	5	1	0
		%	0.0%	33.3%	55.6%	11.1%	0.0%
	41-50 years old	Frequency	3	2	3	3	0
		%	27.3%	18.2%	27.3%	27.3%	0.0%
	over 50 years old	Frequency	4	4	9	2	2
		%	19.0%	19.0%	42.9%	9.5%	9.5%

$\chi^2=7,469$; $df=8$; $p=0,487$

Satisfaction with the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing is similar for teachers, whether they are in university or pre-university settings.

However, those with other professional status are very less satisfied with the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing.

*Cross tab no. 39. Professional status** Are you satisfied with the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing?

			to a very small extent	to a small extent	neither small nor large	largely	to a very large extent
Professional status	University teaching staff	Frequency	2	2	4	2	0
		%	20.0%	20.0%	40.0%	20.0%	0.0%
	Teaching staff in pre-university education	Frequency	2	7	13	4	2
		%	7.1%	25.0%	46.4%	14.3%	7.1%
	Trainer/Education Expert	Frequency	2	0	0	0	0
		%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Active member educational NGO	Frequency	1	0	0	0	0	
	%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	

$\chi^2=17,528$; $df=12$; $p=0,131$

Although there are different weights of satisfaction - with how the administrative capacity of the education system is developing - according to the respondents' professional experience, the differences are not statistically significant.

*Cross tab no. 40. Professional experience?** Are you satisfied with the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing?

			to a very small extent	to a small extent	neither small nor large	largely	to a very large extent
What is your professional experience?	5-10 years old	Frequency	0	2	4	0	0
		%	0.0%	33.3%	66.7%	0.0%	0.0%
	10-20 years old	Frequency	1	3	3	2	0
		%	11.1%	33.3%	33.3%	22.2%	0.0%
	20-30 years old	Frequency	3	3	4	2	0
		%	25.0%	25.0%	33.3%	16.7%	0.0%
	over 30 years old	Frequency	3	1	6	2	2
		%	21.4%	7.1%	42.9%	14.3%	14.3%

$\chi^2=10,528$; $df=12$; $p=0,570$

14. Specify some aspects that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the current dynamics of educational change.

The most important issues that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the current dynamics of educational change are, in the opinion of survey participants, the following: infrastructure development (mentioned by 45% of respondents), good administration (40%) and readiness to change (35%).

Table no. 34. Specify some aspects that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the current dynamics of educational change.

		Responses		Percentage of respondents
		N	Procent	
Specify some aspects that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the current dynamics of educational change.	Development of educational infrastructure	18	37,5%	45,0%
	Adapting to change	14	29,2%	35,0%
	Good governance	16	33,3%	40,0%
Total		48	100,0%	120,0%

The following table shows the weights of the responses on issues that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system, according to the field in which the respondents work. While for those working in the public sector the main issues mentioned were infrastructure development, good administration and adapting to change, for those working in the private sector good administration and adapting to change were the main issues mentioned.

*Cross tab no. 41. Area of professional activity** Specify some aspects that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the current dynamics of educational change

			Public		Privat	
			Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Specify some aspects that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the current dynamics of educational change	Development of educational infrastructure	of	17	48,6%	1	20,0%
	Adapting to change	to	12	34,3%	2	40,0%
	Good governance		13	37,1%	3	60,0%
Total			35		5	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

The vast majority (55.6%) of 31- 40-year-olds felt that good governance was an issue that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the current dynamics of educational change, while no less than 80% of 41-50 years old indicated adaptation to change. People over 50 years of age gave higher proportions to infrastructure development (57.1%) and good administration (33.3%).

*Cross tab no. 42. Age** Specify some aspects that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the current dynamics of educational change

		31-40 years old		41-50 years old		over 50 years old	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Specify some aspects that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the change	Development of educational infrastructure	4	44,4%	2	20,0%	12	57,1%
	Adapting to change	2	22,2%	8	80,0%	4	19,0%

current dynamics of educational change.	Good governance	5	55,6 %	4	40,0 %	7	33,3 %
Total		9		10		21	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

In the table below we can see the weights of the responses, regarding the aspects that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the present dynamics of educational change, according to the professional status of the respondents.

*Cross tab no. 42. * Professional status* Specify some aspects that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the current dynamics of educational change*

		University teaching staff		Teaching staff in pre-university education		Trainer/Education Expert		Active member educational NGO	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Specify some aspects that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the current dynamics of educational change.	Development of educational infrastructure	2	20,0%	16	59,3%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
	Adapting to change	5	50,0%	8	29,6%	1	50,0%	0	0,0%
	Good governance	5	50,0%	8	29,6%	2	100,0%	1	100,0%
Total		10		27		2		1	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

Depending on their work experience, the answers given by respondents on the issues that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the current dynamics of educational change differ, as can be seen in the following table.

Cross tab no. 43. Professional experience Specify some aspects that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system in the current dynamics of educational change*

		5-10 years old		10-20 years old		20-30 years old		over 30 years old	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Specify some aspects that could improve the administrative capacity of the	Development of educational infrastructure	1	16,7%	4	44,4%	4	36,4%	9	64,3%
	Adapting to change	1	16,7%	6	66,7%	4	36,4%	3	21,4%

national education system in the current dynamics of educational change.	Good governance	4	66,7 %	3	33,3%	5	45,5%	4	28,6 %
Total		6		9		11		14	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

15. *What is the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system?*

By far, adaptation to the demands of the socio-economic environment was the most frequent response (78.1% of respondents) to the question what is the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system. Somewhat further away were answers such as: cohesion at structural and functional level (62.5%) and institutional competence and performance (37.5%).

Table no. 35. What is the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system?

		Responses		Percentage of respondents
		N	Procent	
What is the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system?	Structural and functional cohesion	20	35,1%	62,5%
	Institutional competence and performance	12	21,1%	37,5%
	Adaptation to the demands of the socio-economic environment	25	43,9%	78,1%
Total		57	100,0%	178,1%

The following table shows the percentages in which survey participants, grouped according to the field in which they work, indicated the results of the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system.

*Cross tab no. 44. Area of professional activity** What is the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system?

		Public		Privat	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
What is the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system?	Structural and functional cohesion	17	58,6%	3	100,0 %
	Institutional competence and performance	11	37,9%	1	33,3%
	Adaptation to the demands of the socio-economic environment	22	75,9%	3	100,0 %
Total		29		3	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

Although different weights of the results of the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system are mentioned depending on the age of the study participants, the differences are not statistically significant.

*Cross tab no. 45. Age** What is the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system?

		31-40 years old		41-50 years old		over 50 years old	
		Frequen cy	%	Frequen cy	%	Frequen cy	%
What is the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system?	Structural and functional cohesion	4	57,1%	5	62,5%	11	64,7 %
	Institutional competence and performance	6	85,7%	1	12,5%	5	29,4%
	Adaptation to the demands of the socio-economic environment	3	42,9%	7	87,5%	15	88,2%
Total		7		8		17	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

Mentioning the results of the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system was done in similar weights, regardless of the professional status of the respondent, as can be seen in the following table.

*Cross tab no. 46. Professional status** What is the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system?

		University teaching staff		Teaching staff in pre-university education		Trainer/Education Expert	
		Frequen cy	%	Frequen cy	%	Frecuen cy	%
What is the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system?	Structural and functional cohesion	7	77,8%	11	52,4%	2	100,0 %
	Institutional competence and performance	3	33,3%	8	38,1%	1	50,0%
	Adaptation to the demands of the socio-economic environment	7	77,8%	16	76,2%	2	100,0 %
Total		9		21		2	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

The table below shows the percentages in which survey participants, grouped by work experience, indicated the results of the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system.

*Cross tab no. 47. Professional experience** What is the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system?

		5-10 years old		10-20 years old		20-30 years old		over 30 years old	
		Frequen cy	%	Frequen cy	%	Frequen cy	%	Frequen cy	%
What is the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system?	Structural and functional cohesion	2	50,0 %	6	85,7 %	4	50,0 %	8	61,5 %
	Institutional competence and performance	3	75,0 %	4	57,1 %	2	25,0 %	3	23,1 %
	Adaptation to the demands of the socio-economic environment	2	50,0 %	4	57,1 %	6	75,0 %	13	100,0 %
Total		4		7		8		13	

16. State the importance of educational change management for the development of the national education system:

The overwhelming majority of survey participants (95.1%) strongly and very strongly agree with the importance of educational change management for the development of the national education system.

Table no. 36. State the importance of educational change management for the development of the national education system

		Frequency	Percent
Validated date	neither small nor large	2	4,9
	largely	14	34,1
	to a very large extent	25	61,0
	Total	41	100,0

Both public and private sector practitioners believe that educational change management is important for the development of the national education system.

*Cross tab no. 48. Professional activity** State the importance of educational change management for the development of the national education system

		neither small nor large		largely		to a very large extent	
		Frequen cy	%	Frequen cy	%	Frequen cy	%
Your area of professional activity	Public	Frequen cy	1	13	22		
		%	2.8%	36.1%	61.1%		
	Privat	Frequen cy	1	1	3		
		%	20.0%	20.0%	60.0%		

$\chi^2=3,004$; $df=2$; $p=0,223$

The level of importance of educational change management for the development of the national education system is similar for all study participants, regardless of their age.

*Cross tab no. 49. Age** State the importance of educational change management for the development of the national education system

			neither nor large	small largely	to a very large extent
Age	31-40 years old	Frequency	1	4	4
		%	11.1%	44.4%	44.4%
	41-50 years old	Frequency	0	3	8
		%	0.0%	27.3%	72.7%
	over 50 years old	Frequency	1	7	13
		%	4.8%	33.3%	61.9%

$\chi^2=2,345$; $df=4$; $p=0,673$

In the following table, the frequencies and weights of the answers given by the respondents regarding the level of importance of educational change management for the development of the national education system can be traced by professional status. They do not differ significantly.

*Cross tab no. 50. Professional status** State the importance of educational change management for the development of the national education system

			neither nor large	small largely	to a very large extent
Professional status	University teaching staff	Frequency	1	1	8
		%	10.0%	10.0%	80.0%
	Teaching staff in pre- university education	Frequency	1	12	15
		%	3.6%	42.9%	53.6%
	Trainer/Education Expert	Frequency	0	0	2
		%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
Active member educational NGO	Frequency	0	1	0	
	%	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%	

$\chi^2=7,019$; $df=6$; $p=0,319$

Although different weights of the degree of importance of educational change management for the development of the national education system are observed according to the professional experience of the respondents, the differences are not statistically significant.

*Cross tab no. 51. Professional experience** State the importance of educational change management for the development of the national education system

			neither nor large	small largely	to a very large extent	
What is your professional experience?	5-10 years old	Frequency	1	2	3	
		%	16.7%	33.3%	50.0%	
	10-20 years old	Frequency	0	5	4	
		%	0.0%	55.6%	44.4%	
			Frequency	0	5	7

20-30 years old	%	0.0%	41.7%	58.3%
over 30 years old	Frequency	1	2	11
	%	7.1%	14.3%	78.6%

$\chi^2=7,153$; $df=6$; $p=0,307$

17. *What are the dimensions of educational change management?*

According to those questioned, the following dimensions ensure the management of educational change: the administrative-managerial dimension, mentioned by 51.2% of participants, the axiological dimension (22%), the socio-economic dimension (19.5%) and the psychological dimension (7.3%). The reference to the administrative-managerial dimension in particular calls for greater attention to be paid by the decision-makers involved in the process of educational change.

Table no. 37. **What are the dimensions of educational change management?**

	Frequency	Percent
axiological dimension	9	22.0
the socio-economic dimension	8	19.5
Validated date the administrative-managerial dimension	21	51.2
psychological dimension	3	7.3
Total	41	100.0

We note that both those working in the public sector and those working in the private sector have mostly specified the administrative-managerial dimension as the main dimension ensuring educational change management.

Cross tab no. 52. **Area of professional activity*** What are the dimensions of educational change management?

			axiological dimension	the socio-economic dimension	the administrative-managerial dimension	psychological dimension
Your area of professional activity	Public	Frequency	8	8	17	3
		%	22.2%	22.2%	47.2%	8.3%
	Private	Frequency	1	0	4	0
		%	20.0%	0.0%	80.0%	0.0%

$\chi^2=2,459$; $df=3$; $p=0,483$

The following table shows the weight of each dimension of educational change management according to the age of the respondents. Regardless of the age category of the respondents, the administrative-managerial dimension was specified by the majority of respondents.

*Cross tab no. 53. Age** What are the dimensions of educational change management?

			axiological dimension	the socio-economic dimension	the administrative-managerial dimension	psychological dimension
Age	31-40 years old	Frequency	0	2	7	0
		%	0.0%	22.2%	77.8%	0.0%
	41-50 years old	Frequency	2	2	7	0
		%	18.2%	18.2%	63.6%	0.0%
	over 50 years old	Frecvența	7	4	7	3
		%	33.3%	19.0%	33.3%	14.3%

$\chi^2=9,072$; $df=6$; $p=0,170$

Regardless of their professional status, a high proportion of respondents mentioned the administrative-managerial dimension as important in educational change management.

*Cross tab no. 54. Professional status** What are the dimensions of educational change management?

			axiological dimension	the socio-economic dimension	the administrative-managerial dimension	psychological dimension
Professional status	University teaching staff	Frequency	2	2	6	0
		%	20.0%	20.0%	60.0%	0.0%
	Teaching staff in pre-university education	Frequency	6	5	14	3
		%	21.4%	17.9%	50.0%	10.7%
	Trainer/Education Expert	Frequency	0	1	1	0
		%	0.0%	50.0%	50.0%	0.0%
Active member educational NGO	Frequency	1	0	0	0	
	%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	

$\chi^2=6,488$; $df=9$; $p=0,690$

The percentage of those who mentioned the administrative-managerial dimension is also high for the different categories of work experience.

*Cross tab no. 55. Professional experience** What are the dimensions of educational change management?

			axiological dimension	the socio-economic dimension	the administrative-managerial dimension	psychological dimension
What is your professional experience?	5-10 years old	Frequency	1	1	4	0
		%	16.7%	16.7%	66.7%	0.0%
	10-20 years old	Frequency	1	2	6	0
		%	11.1%	22.2%	66.7%	0.0%
	20-30 years old	Frequency	2	4	6	0
		%	16.7%	33.3%	50.0%	0.0%
	over 30 years old	Frequency	5	1	5	3
		%	35.7%	7.1%	35.7%	21.4%

$\chi^2=11,395$; $df=9$; $p=0,250$

18. *To what extent do you consider that educational change management responds to the challenges of today?*

Opinions on the extent to which educational change management responds to the challenges of today are divided among the participants in the survey. 53.7% think to a great or very great extent that it responds to the challenges of the present, 26.9% think it responds to a small or very small extent, while 19.5% have a neutral opinion.

Table no. 37. To what extent do you consider that educational change management responds to the challenges of today?

		Frequency	Procent
Validated date	very small extent	2	4.9
	small extent	9	22.0
	neither small nor large	8	19.5
	largely	13	31.7
	to a very large extent	9	22.0
	Total	41	100.0

Those working in the private sector are divided on the extent to which educational change management is responding to today's challenges. People working in the public sector have the following opinions: 25% have a negative opinion, 19.4% have a neutral opinion and 55.5% have a positive opinion, they believe that educational change management responds to the challenges of today to a great and very great extent. Although differences can be observed between those in the private and public sector, the result of the statistical analysis shows that they are, however, not statistically significant.

Cross tab no. 56. Area of professional activity* To what extent do you consider that educational change management responds to the challenges of today?

			very small extent	small extent	neither small nor large	largely	to a very large extent
Your area of professional activity	Public	Frequency	1	8	7	12	8
		%	2.8%	22.2%	19.4%	33.3%	22.2%
	Privat	Frequency	1	1	1	1	1
		%	20.0%	20.0%	20.0%	20.0%	20.0%

$\chi^2=2,936$; $df=4$; $p=0,569$

The following table shows the frequencies and weights of respondents' answers on the extent to which they believe that educational change management responds to today's challenges, by age. While younger people have a slightly higher proportion of neutral or negative views, the proportion of those who have a positive view of the extent to which educational change management responds to the challenges of today increases with age.

Cross tab no. 57. Age* To what extent do you consider that educational change management responds to the challenges of today?

			very small extent	small extent	neither small nor large	largely	to a very large extent
Age	31-40 years old	Frequency	0	3	3	1	2
		%	0,0%	33,3%	33,3%	11,1%	22,2%
	41-50 years old	Frequency	1	3	2	3	2
		%	9,1%	27,3%	18,2%	27,3%	18,2%

over 50 years old	Frequency	1	3	3	9	5
	%	4,8%	14,3%	14,3%	42,9%	23,8%

$\chi^2=5,460$; $df=8$; $p=0,707$

In the table below we can see the weights of the answers according to the professional status of the respondents. There is no significant association between professional status and opinion on the extent to which they believe that educational change management responds to today's challenges ($\chi^2=11.956$; $df=12$; $p=0.449$).

*Cross tab no. 58. Professional status** To what extent do you consider that educational change management responds to the challenges of today?

			very small extent	small extent	neither small nor large	largely	to a very large extent
Professional status	University teaching staff	Frequency	1	1	3	3	2
		%	10,0%	10,0%	30,0%	30,0%	20,0%
	Teaching staff in pre-university education	Frequency	1	8	5	9	5
		%	3,6%	28,6%	17,9%	32,1%	17,9%
	Trainer/Education Expert	Frequency	0	0	0	0	2
		%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%
	Active member educational NGO	Frequency	0	0	0	1	0
		%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	0,0%

$\chi^2=11,956$; $df=12$; $p=0,449$

Below are how the survey participants, grouped according to their work experience, responded to the question “to what extent do you think educational change management responds to today’s challenges?”. Thus, 35.7% of respondents with more than 30 years’ professional experience answered to a great extent/very great extent, 50% of respondents with 20-30 years’ experience answered to a great extent and 44.4% of respondents with 10-20 years’ experience answered to a very great extent. It can be seen that the response weights are not statistically significantly different.

*Cross tab no. 59. Professional experience** To what extent do you consider that educational change management responds to the challenges of today?

			very small extent	small extent	neither small nor large	largely	to a very large extent
What is your professional experience?	5-10 years old	Frequency	0	1	4	1	0
		%	0,0%	16,7%	66,7%	16,7%	0,0%
	10-20 years old	Frequency	0	4	0	1	4
		%	0,0%	44,4%	0,0%	11,1%	44,4%
	20-30 years old	Frequency	1	2	3	6	0
		%	8,3%	16,7%	25,0%	50,0%	0,0%
	over 30 years old	Frequency	1	2	1	5	5
		%	7,1%	14,3%	7,1%	35,7%	35,7%

$\chi^2=23,930$; $df=12$; $p=0,061$

19. *What are the determinants of effective educational change management?*

51.2% of the participants in the survey indicated all factors as drivers of effective educational change management. Of the remaining respondents, 22% mentioned institutional responsibility and accountability, 19.5% mentioned cohesion of educational provision and the labor market and 7.3% mentioned institutional transparency and integrity. It can be concluded that institutional responsibility and accountability is the main driver of effective educational change management in the view of the respondents, followed closely by cohesion, educational provision and the labor market.

Table no. 38. **What are the determinants of effective educational change management?**

		Frequency	Procent
Validated date	Institutional responsibility and accountability	9	22.0
	Cohesion of education provision and the labor market	8	19.5
	Transparency and institutional integrity	3	7.3
	All options	21	51.2
	Total	41	100.0

Almost all private sector respondents mentioned all the factors presented as determinants of the effectiveness of educational change management, while only 47.2% of public sector respondents mentioned all the options as valid.

Cross tab no. 60. **Professional activity*** What are the determinants of effective educational change management?

			Institutional responsibility and accountability	Cohesion of education provision and the labor market	Transparency and institutional integrity	All options
Your area of professional activity	Public	Frequency	9	7	3	17
		%	25.0%	19.4%	8.3%	47.2%
	Privat	Frequency	0	1	0	4
		%	0.0%	20.0%	0.0%	80.0%

$\chi^2=2,588$; $df=3$; $p=0,460$

The vast majority of people aged over 50 (71.4%) believe that all the factors presented here are factors that make educational change management more effective. In the case of 31–40-year-olds, the share of those who believe that all the factors presented are drivers of effective educational change management is 55.6%, while in the case of 41–50-year-olds the share of those who believe that all the factors presented are drivers of effective educational change management is very low (9.1%), with the vast majority (45.5%) mentioning only cohesion, educational supply and the labor market as the main drivers of effective educational change management.

The results obtained from the chi-square test, which indicates the association between age and the specification of the generating factors of educational change management effectiveness, show that it is statistically significant ($\chi^2=14.138$; $df=6$; $p=0.028$).

*Cross tab no. 61. Age** What are the determinants of effective educational change management?

		Institutional responsibility and accountability	Cohesion of education provision and the labor market	Transparency and institutional integrity	All options	
Age	31-40 years old	Frequency	2	2	0	5
		%	22.2%	22.2%	0.0%	55.6%
	41-50 years old	Frequency	4	5	1	1
		%	36.4%	45.5%	9.1%	9.1%
	over 50 years old	Frequency	3	1	2	15
		%	14.3%	4.8%	9.5%	71.4%

$\chi^2=14,138$; $df=6$; $p=0,028$; Cramer's $V=0,415$

The results of the chi-square test refute the presence of a significant association between professional status and the specification of the factors generating the effectiveness of educational change management. Regardless of their professional status, at least half of the respondents mentioned all the factors presented as generators of educational change management effectiveness.

*Cross tab no. 62. Professional status** What are the determinants of effective educational change management?

		Institutional responsibility and accountability	Cohesion of education provision and the labor market	Transparency and institutional integrity	All options	
Professional status	University teaching staff	Frequency	2	2	1	5
		%	20.0%	20.0%	10.0%	50.0%
	Teaching staff in pre-university education	Frequency	7	5	2	14
		%	25.0%	17.9%	7.1%	50.0%
	Trainer/Education Expert	Frequency	0	1	0	1
		%	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	50.0%
	Active member educational NGO	Frequency	0	0	0	1
		%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%

$\chi^2=2,778$; $df=9$; $p=0,972$

In the table below, the percentages in which the study participants, grouped according to their work experience, indicated the factors that generate the effectiveness of educational change management can be seen. No statistically significant differences were found between people in the different categories of work experience.

*Cross tab no. 63. Professional experience** What are the determinants of effective educational change management?

			Institutional responsibility and accountability	Cohesion of education provision and the labor market	Transparency and institutional integrity	All options
What is your professional experience?	5-10 years old	Frequency	2	1	0	3
		%	33.3%	16.7%	0.0%	50.0%
	10-20 years old	Frequency	2	3	0	4
		%	22.2%	33.3%	0.0%	44.4%
	20-30 years old	Frequency	2	3	3	4
		%	16.7%	25.0%	25.0%	33.3%
	over 30 years old	Frequency	3	1	0	10
		%	21.4%	7.1%	0.0%	71.4%

$\chi^2=11,896$; $df=9$; $p=0,219$

20. Which form of responsibility should be reflected in educational change management?

While 24.4% said that only administrative-legal responsibility should be part of educational change management and 4.9% said only public accountability, the majority of respondents (70.7%) said that all forms of accountability should be part of educational change management.

Table no. 39. Which form of responsibility should be reflected in educational change management?

		Frequency	Procent
Validated date	Administrative-legal responsibility	10	24.4
	Public responsibility	2	4.9
	All options	29	70.7
	Total	41	100.0

80% of those working in the private sector said that all forms of accountability should be reflected in educational change management, while 69.4% of those working in the public sector said that all of them were valid.

*Cross tab no. 64. Area of professional activity** Which form of responsibility should be reflected in educational change management?

			Administrative-legal responsibility	Public responsibility	All options
Your area of professional activity	Public	Frequency	9	2	25
		%	25.0%	5.6%	69.4%
	Privat	Frequency	1	0	4
		%	20.0%	0.0%	80.0%

$\chi^2=0,392$; $df=2$; $p=0,822$

In the following table, it is possible to trace the weight of the forms of responsibility that should be found in educational change management, according to the age of the respondents. Irrespective of the age category they belong to, more than 60% of the respondents mentioned that all forms of responsibility should be reflected in educational change management.

*Cross tab no. 65. Age** Which form of responsibility should be reflected in educational change management?

			Administrative- legal responsibility	Public responsibility	All options
Age	31-40 years old	Frequency	1	1	7
		%	11.1%	11.1%	77.8%
	41-50 years old	Frequency	4	0	7
		%	36.4%	0.0%	63.6%
	over 50 years old	Frequency	5	1	15
		%	23.8%	4.8%	71.4%

$\chi^2=2,697$; $df=4$; $p=0,610$

Regardless of their professional status, a large proportion of respondents mentioned that all forms of accountability should be reflected in educational change management.

*Cross tab no. 66. Professional status** Which form of responsibility should be reflected in educational change management?

			Administrative- legal responsibility	Public responsibility	All options
Professio nal status		Frequency	4	0	6
		%	40.0%	0.0%	60.0%
		Frequency	6	2	20
		%	21.4%	7.1%	71.4%
		Frequency	0	0	2
		%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0 %
		Frequency	0	0	1
		%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0 %

$\chi^2=3,288$; $df=6$; $p=0,772$

And for the different categories of work experience, the percentage of those who mentioned that all forms of responsibility should be reflected in educational change management is high, over 66% in each category of work experience.

*Cross tab no. 67. Professional experience** Which form of responsibility should be reflected in educational change management?

				Administrative -legal responsibility	Public responsibility	All options
What is your professional experience?	5-10 old	years	Frequency	0	1	5
			%	0.0%	16.7%	83.3%
	10-20 old	years	Frequency	3	0	6
			%	33.3%	0.0%	66.7%
	20-30 old	years	Frequency	4	0	8
			%	33.3%	0.0%	66.7%
over 30 old	years	Frequency	3	1	10	
		%	21.4%	7.1%	71.4%	

$\chi^2=5,268$; $df=6$; $p=0,510$

21. *What does institutional accountability relate to in the context of educational change management?*

Professional accountability was by far the most common response (87.8% of respondents) to the question. Quite far behind were answers such as funding accountability (43.9%) and market accountability (39%).

Table no. 40. What does institutional accountability relate to in the context of educational change management?

			Responses		Percentage of respondents
			N	Procent	
What does institutional accountability relate to in the context of educational change management?	professional accountability		36	51.4%	87.8%
		market accountability	16	22.9%	39.0%
		accountability financing	18	25.7%	43.9%
Total			70	100.0%	170.7%

Regardless of their field of activity, respondents gave similar answers to the question.

*Cross tab no. 68. Professional activity** What does institutional accountability relate to in the context of educational change management?

			professional accountability	market accountability	accountability financing
Your area of Public professional activity	Public	Frequency	31	14	16
		%	86.1%	38.9%	44.4%
	Privat	Frequency	5	2	2
		%	100.0%	40.0%	40.0%

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

Although different weights of answers are given depending on the age of the study participants, the differences are not statistically significant.

*Cross tab no. 69. Age** What does institutional accountability relate to in the context of educational change management?

			professional accountability	market accountability	accountability financing
Age	31-40 years old	Frequency	7	5	4
		%	77.8%	55.6%	44.4%
	41-50 years old	Frequency	10	3	6
		%	90.9%	27.3%	54.5%
	over 50 years old	Frequency	19	8	8
		%	90.5%	38.1%	38.1%

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

There are also no significant differences in the grouping of respondents by professional status in their responses to what institutional accountability is reported in the context of educational change management.

*Cross tab no. 70. Professional status** What does institutional accountability relate to in the context of educational change management?

			professional accountability	market accounta bility	accounta bility financing
Professional status	University teaching staff	Frequency	8	5	2
		%	80.0%	50.0%	20.0%
	Teaching staff in pre- university education	Frequency	26	10	14
		%	92.9%	35.7%	50.0%
	Trainer/Education Expert	Frequency	2	1	1
		%	100.0%	50.0%	50.0%
	Active member educational NGO	Frequency	0	0	1
		%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

Below are how the study participants, grouped by work experience, answered the question. The share of responses does not differ statistically significantly.

*Cross tab no. 70. What is your professional experience? * What does institutional accountability relate to in the context of educational change management?*

			professional accountability	market accounta bility	accounta bility financing
What is your professional experience?	5-10 years old	Frequency	4	4	2
		%	66.7%	66.7%	33.3%
	10-20 years old	Frequency	9	2	3
		%	100.0%	22.2%	33.3%
	20-30 years old	Frequency	9	5	8
		%	75.0%	41.7%	66.7%
	over 30 years old	Frequency	14	5	5
		%	100.0%	35.7%	35.7%

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

22. *What are the necessary directions for integration market-education-work cohesion?*

The directions needed to integrate market-education-labour cohesion, in descending order of the number of mentions by respondents, are the following: linking the educational offer to the labour market demand (mentioned by 63.4% of respondents), developing the cult of education and work (56.1%), adapting the educational offer to the geographical, industrial, social area (53.7%) and developing the cult of profession and professionalism (48.8%).

Table no. 41. What are the necessary directions for integration market-education-work cohesion?

		Responses		Percentage of respondents
		N	Procent	
What are the necessary directions for integration market-education-work cohesion?	development of the cult of education and work	23	25.3%	56.1%
	development of the cult of profession and professionalism	20	22.0%	48.8%
	connecting educational provision with labor market demand	26	28.6%	63.4%
	adapting educational provision to the geographical, industrial and social area	22	24.2%	53.7%
Total		91	100.0%	222.0%

In the following table, the percentages in which survey participants, grouped according to their field of work, indicated the directions needed to integrate market-education-work cohesion can be seen.

Cross tab no. 71. Professional activity What are the necessary directions for integration market-education-work cohesion?*

Your area of professional activity:			development of the cult of education and work	development of the cult of profession and professionalis	connecting educational provision with labor market demand	adapting educational provision to the geographical, industrial and social area
			Frequency	Frequency	Frequency	Frequency
Public	Frequency	19	17	23	20	
	%	52.8%	47.2%	63.9%	55.6%	
Privat	Frequency	4	3	3	2	
	%	80.0%	60.0%	60.0%	40.0%	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

Mention of the directions needed to integrate market-education-work cohesion was made in similar proportions, regardless of the age of the respondents.

*Cross tab no. 72. Age** What are the necessary directions for integration market-education-work cohesion?

			develop ment of the cult of educatio n and work	development of the cult of profession and professio nalis	connecting educational provision with labor market demand	adapting educational provision to the geographical, industrial and social area
Age	31-40 years old	Frequency	5	5	6	3
		%	55.6%	55.6%	66.7%	33.3%
	41-50 years old	Frequency	7	6	8	7
		%	63.6%	54.5%	72.7%	63.6%
	over 50 years old	Frequency	11	9	12	12
		%	52.4%	42.9%	57.1%	57.1%

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

Even when grouping respondents by professional status, there are no significant differences between their responses regarding the directions needed to integrate market-education-work cohesion.

*Cross tab no. 73. Professional status** What are the necessary directions for integration market-education-work cohesion?

			develop ment of the cult of education and work	development of the cult of profession and professio nalis	connecting educational provision with labor market demand	adapting educational provision to the geographical , industrial and social area
Professio nal status	University teaching staff	Frequency	5	3	8	4
		%	50.0%	30.0%	80.0%	40.0%
	Teaching staff in pre-university education	Frequency	16	16	15	16
		%	57.1%	57.1%	53.6%	57.1%
	Trainer/Education Expert	Frequency	2	1	2	1
		%	100.0%	50.0%	100.0%	50.0%
	Active member educational NGO	Frequency	0	0	1	1
		%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

Below are how the study participants, grouped according to work experience, identified the directions needed to integrate market-education-work cohesion. The share of responses does not differ statistically significantly.

*Cross tab no. 74. Professional experience** What are the necessary directions for integration market-education-work cohesion?

			develop ment of the cult of education and work	development of the cult of profession and professio nalis	connecting educational provision with labor market demand	adapting educational provision to the geographical , industrial and social area
What is your professional experience?	5-10 years old	Frequency %	3 50.0%	2 33.3%	6 100.0%	3 50.0%
	10-20 years old	Frequency %	6 66.7%	5 55.6%	5 55.6%	4 44.4%
	20-30 years old	Frequency %	4 33.3%	5 41.7%	7 58.3%	8 66.7%
	over 30 years old	Frequency %	10 71.4%	8 57.1%	8 57.1%	7 50.0%

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

23. *What are the elements that converge to support the link between integrity and institutional transparency in ensuring educational change management?*

The most frequent response (80.5% of respondents) to the question was respect for professional ethics. Far behind were answers such as: visibility and access to decision-making (56.1%), respect for fundamental human rights and freedoms (53.7%), working in the spirit of organizational values (34.1%), and executing legal rules in good faith (24.4%). The answers given by respondents are close to the realities of the national education system. Moreover, they contribute to the identification of relevant solutions necessary to support the institutional integrity-transparency link in ensuring educational change management.

Table no. 42. What are the elements that converge to support the link between integrity and institutional transparency in ensuring educational change management?

		Responses		Percentage of respondents
		N	Procent	
What are the elements that converge to support the link between integrity and institutional transparency in ensuring educational change management?	respect for professional ethics	33	32.4%	80.5%
	performing in good faith legal rules	10	9.8%	24.4%
	respect for fundamental human rights and freedoms	22	21.6%	53.7%
	visibility and access to the decision-making process	23	22.5%	56.1%
	working in the spirit of organisational values	14	13.7%	34.1%
Total		102	100.0%	248.8%

Although there are different proportions of responses depending on the field in which the participants work, the differences are not statistically significant.

*Cross tab no. 75. Professional activity** What are the elements that converge to support the link between integrity and institutional transparency in ensuring educational change management?

			respect for professional ethics	performing in good faith legal rules	respect for fundamental human rights and freedoms	visibility and access to the decision-making process	working in the spirit of organisational values
Your area of professional activity	Public	Frequency	28	7	19	21	14
		%	77.8%	19.4%	52.8%	58.3%	38.9%
	Privat	Frequency	5	3	3	2	0
		%	100.0%	60.0%	60.0%	40.0%	0.0%

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents

Regardless of age, the ranking of the nomination of elements that converge to support the integrity-institutional transparency link in ensuring educational change management is similar.

*Cross tab no. 76. Age** What are the elements that converge to support the link between integrity and institutional transparency in ensuring educational change management?

			respect for professional ethics	performing in good faith legal rules	respect for fundamental human rights and freedoms	visibility and access to the decision-making process	working in the spirit of organizational values
Age	31-40 years old	Frequency	8	1	5	4	4
		%	88.9%	11.1%	55.6%	44.4%	44.4%
	41-50 years old	Frequency	8	3	6	8	3
		%	72.7%	27.3%	54.5%	72.7%	27.3%
	over 50 years old	Frequency	17	6	11	11	7
		%	81.0%	28.6%	52.4%	52.4%	33.3%

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

Even in the case of grouping respondents by professional status, there are no significant differences between their responses to the question asked and the elements that converge in support of the integrity-institutional transparency link in ensuring educational change management.

*Cross tab no. 77. Professional status** What are the elements that converge to support the link between integrity and institutional transparency in ensuring educational change management?

			respect for professional ethics	performing in good faith legal rules	respect for fundamental human rights and freedoms	visibility and access to the decision-making process	working in the spirit of organizational values
Professional status	University teaching staff	Frequency	9	3	4	3	3
		%	90.0%	30.0%	40.0%	30.0%	30.0%
	Teaching staff in pre-university education	Frequency	21	6	17	17	10
		%	75.0%	21.4%	60.7%	60.7%	35.7%
	Trainer/Education Expert	Frequency	2	1	1	2	0
	%	100.0%	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%	0.0%	
Active member educational NGO	Frequency	1	0	0	1	1	
	%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

Below, it is presented how the participants in the study, grouped according to their professional experience, specified the elements that converge to support the integrity-institutional transparency link in ensuring educational change management. The weights of the responses are not statistically significantly different.

*Cross tab no. 78. Professional experience** What are the elements that converge to support the link between integrity and institutional transparency in ensuring educational change management?

			respect for professional ethics	performing in good faith legal rules	respect for fundamental human rights and freedoms	visibility and access to the decision-making process	working in the spirit of organisational values
What is your professional experience?	5-10 years old	Frequency	5	1	2	4	3
		%	83.3%	16.7%	33.3%	66.7%	50.0%
	10-20 years old	Frequency	6	1	6	4	3
		%	66.7%	11.1%	66.7%	44.4%	33.3%
	20-30 years old	Frequency	9	2	5	9	3
		%	75.0%	16.7%	41.7%	75.0%	25.0%
over 30 years old	Frequency	13	6	9	6	5	
	%	92.9%	42.9%	64.3%	42.9%	35.7%	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

24. *What are the priorities of educational change management for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system?*

In the opinion of the participants in the survey, the priorities of educational change management for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system are, in order: good governance (mentioned by 41.2% of respondents), flexibility to change (35.3%), development of institutional resources (35.3%), and cohesion between educational provision and the labor market (23.5%).

Table no. 43. What are the priorities of educational change management for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system?

		Responses		Percentage of respondents
		N	Procent	
What are the priorities of educational change management for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system?	Flexibility to change	12	25,5%	35,3%
	Coherence between educational offer and labor market	9	19,1%	26,5%
	Development of institutional resources	12	25,5%	35,3%
	Good governance	14	29,8%	41,2%
Total		47	100,0%	138,2%

The following table shows the percentages in which survey participants, grouped according to the field in which they work, indicated educational change management priorities for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system. Given the small number of people in the sample working in the private sector, the weights of responses are different from those working in the public sector, but the differences are not statistically significant.

Cross tab no. 79. Professional activity* What are the priorities of educational change management for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system?

		Public		Privat	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
What are the priorities of educational change management for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system?	Flexibility to change	11	37,9%	1	20,0%
	Coherence between educational offer and labor market	8	27,6%	1	20,0%
	Development of institutional resources	10	34,5%	2	40,0%
	Good governance	10	34,5%	4	80,0%
Total		29		5	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

Although different weights of answers are given depending on the age of the study participants, the differences are not statistically significant.

*Cross tab no. 80. Age** What are the priorities of educational change management for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system?

		31-40 years old		41-50 years old		over 50 years old	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
What are the priorities of educational change management for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system?	Flexibility to change	4	44,4%	2	28,6%	6	33,3%
	Coherence between educational offer and labor market	2	22,2%	3	42,9%	4	22,2%
	Development of institutional resources	2	22,2%	3	42,9%	7	38,9%
	Good governance	4	44,4%	2	28,6%	8	44,4%
Total		9		7		18	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

Below are how study participants, grouped by professional status, specified educational change management priorities for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system.

*Cross tab no. 80. Professional status** What are the priorities of educational change management for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system?

		University teaching staff		Teaching staff in pre-university education		Trainer/Education Expert		Active member educational NGO	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
What are the priorities of educational change management for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system?	Flexibility to change	2	22,2%	8	36,4%	1	50,0%	1	100,0%
	Coherence between educational offer and labor market	2	22,2%	5	22,7%	2	100,0%	0	0,0%
	Development of institutional resources	2	22,2%	10	45,5%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
	Good governance	5	55,6%	9	40,9%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%
Total		9		22		2		1	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

According to work experience, the answers given by respondents with on educational change management priorities for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system differ slightly, as can be seen in the table below.

*Cross tab no. 81. Professional experience** What are the priorities of educational change management for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system?

		5-10 years old		10-20 years old		20-30 years old		over 30 years old	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
What are the priorities of educational change management for affirming and increasing administrative capacity in the education system?	Flexibility to change	2	33,3 %	3	37,5 %	3	42,9 %	4	30,8 %
	Coherence between educational offer and labor market	1	16,7 %	4	50,0 %	1	14,3 %	3	23,1 %
	Development of institutional resources	1	16,7 %	2	25,0 %	4	57,1 %	5	38,5 %
	Good governance	4	66,7 %	2	25,0 %	2	28,6 %	6	46,2 %
Total		6		8		7		13	

Percentages are reported on the number of respondents.

25. *Do you consider that the management of educational change has a considerable contribution to make to the good management of the national education system?*

The overwhelming majority of respondents (94.9% of valid responses) believe that educational change management makes a considerable contribution to the achievement of good governance of the national education system.

Table no. 44. Do you consider that the management of educational change has a considerable contribution to make to the good management of the national education system?

		Frequency	Percentage of total survey	Percentage of validated data
Validated date	Yes	37	90,2	94,9
	No	2	4,9	5,1
	Total	39	95,1	100,0
Missing data		2	4,9	
Total		41	100,0	

The data collected provides answers, which reinforce the vital role and fundamental importance given to educational change for good governance of the education system, with a focus on administrative capacity development. Such a vision leads the research to identify valuable conclusions on the development of the administrative capacity of the national education system in the context of educational change management.

Conclusions

Quantitative research undertaken provides valuable information to validate the hypothesis that if there is a connection between the administrative capacity of the national education system and the management of educational change, then we will find that the development of educational infrastructure, good administration and the efficiency of change management contribute to the evolution of the national education system. Thus, the model to be followed is about linking educational change management with administrative and legislative issues, with a focus on administrative capacity development. In this context, adaptation to change implies the perspective of good educational management coupled with administrative capacity development. It is essential to emphasize that administrative mechanisms need greater convergence with managerial mechanisms to build a strong linkage to deliver and fulfil the national education service. The idea of connectedness lies in reinventing and adapting educational management, based on educational change, which leaves room for adaptation, innovation and progress. Such an approach produces an inevitable evolution for the administrative capacity of the education system, since "reinvention is the only possible option" (Mureşan 2012, 59). Naturally, the answers provided by respondents converge on the existence of a link between increasing administrative capacity and managing educational change management. Accordingly, more than half of the respondents (53.7%) strongly and very strongly believe that there is a connection between the administrative capacity of the education system and the management of educational change. At the same time, a higher proportion (55.5%) of those working in the public sector believe that there is a strong or very strong relationship between the administrative capacity of the education system and the management of educational change, while the proportion of those working in the private sector who agree to the same extent with the existence of this relationship is lower (40%). Moreover, the proportion of teachers who strongly and very strongly believe that there is a connection between the administrative capacity of the education system and the management of educational change is significantly higher than the proportion of people with other professional status, they agree.

For the national education system, alignment with the "national system of public administration, standards and requirements of the European Union" (*Ibidem*) is the essence of implementing change management. Therefore, 63.4% of the participants in the survey considered that all actions such as planning, organization, predictability and adaptation to change ensure a good connection between administrative capacity and educational change management. Moreover, 53.7% of respondents mentioned the balance between the vision of public authorities and the national interest in education as an element that determines a good management of the connection between administrative capacity and educational change management. Similar percentages were also mentioned by those who mentioned efficient management of educational resources (46.3%) and inter- and intrainstitutional dialogue (41.5%).

Throughout the research presented, even though there is interest in developing the administrative capacity of the national education system by accelerating change management, a number of inequities stand out. These are reflected in the demographic potential, the degree of assimilation of transversal skills among the resident school/student population, the insufficient material base in rural and sometimes urban areas, the limited access to digital resources, their poor quality or non-existence especially in rural areas. All these inequalities in educational infrastructure call into question the modernization and attainment of quality standards in education in the context of increasing the administrative capacity of the national education system. Based on these considerations, the research captured the important elements for increasing the administrative capacity of the national education system in the context of educational change management. As a result, 58.5% of respondents opted for the development of educational infrastructure, 51.2% for good management of the education system and 46.3% for strategic planning. In this context, investment in the infrastructure of the national education system must become a national priority,

as limiting it has adverse consequences for the development of education. All over the world, access to learning environments is closely correlated with the performance of the educational population, and social inequalities, especially educational inequalities, reinforce the negative effects that economic conditions have on performance of all kinds.

In the process of educational change, qualitative transformations have been distinguished at the level of infrastructure, which in the opinion of 85.4% of the respondents concern the human resource, agent of change in education, and in the opinion of 48.8% of the respondents the material resource. In the investigative journey undertaken, institutional resources become agents of educational paradigm change, facilitating a strong transformation process. This process is achieved through personal and collective efforts to adapt to educational change. If investments in human and material resources meet the essential needs of the national education system, and if the adaptation of new technologies to new contexts is associated with the development of transversal competences, then the engine of accessibility, efficiency, competitiveness and inclusion will be able to operate through “eLearning, eGovernment, eHealth” (Efraim Turban, Judy Whiteside, David King, 2017, pp. 137-163). services as fundamental elements of educational change and innovation. Investment in educational infrastructure can therefore be developed through a holistic set of criteria, integrated into a unified strategic framework, underpinned by good governance of the education system.

Factors influencing the development of the administrative capacity of the national education system were also identified in the context of the questionnaire. Almost two thirds of respondents (61%) indicated that professional development through strengthening professional, decision-making and pedagogical competence areas is the major factor influencing the administrative capacity of the education system. At the same time, the study provides valuable insights into the impact of educational change management on the administrative capacity of the national education system. The most frequent response was for adaptation to the demands of the socio-economic environment, according to 78.1% of respondents, followed by 62.5% for cohesion at structural and functional level, 37.5% for institutional competence and performance. The options indicated by respondents contribute greatly to the formulation of clear directions on the need for change in the education system on the adaptation-cohesion-competence axis.

As only 39.1% of the respondents are only slightly and very slightly satisfied with the way the administrative capacity of the education system is developing and only 19.5% of the survey participants are very and very slightly satisfied with the way the administrative capacity of the national education system is developing, we considered it necessary to identify priority issues for improving the administrative capacity of the national education system in the current dynamics of educational change. Thus, the most important issues that could improve the administrative capacity of the national education system are, in the opinion of the survey participants, the following: 39.5% efficiency of change management, 39.5% adaptation to change and 36.8% good administration.

In this context, the mission of public administration and change management in the education system is to meet the standards of good governance and develop the administrative capacity of the national education system. In this respect, it is confirmed by the overwhelming majority of respondents, 94.9% of valid responses, that educational change management has a considerable contribution to make in achieving good administration of the national education system. The overwhelming majority of respondents (95.1%) also strongly and very strongly agree with the importance of educational change management for the development of the national education system. At the same time, the dimensions that ensure educational change management were identified. According to the opinion of the respondents, 51.2% appreciate the administrative-managerial dimension, 22% the axiological dimension, 19.5% the socio-economic dimension, 7.3% the psychological dimension.

From the perspective of linking educational change management to the challenges of today, respondents' opinions are divided, as follows: 53.7% believe to a great and very great extent that it responds to the challenges of today, 26.9% believe that it responds to a small and very small extent, while 19.5% have a neutral opinion. Relating the effectiveness of educational change management

to specific drivers, in the opinion of the research participants, 51.2% indicated that all factors (institutional responsibility and accountability, coherence of educational provision and the labor market, transparency and institutional integrity) were important, and the majority of the research participants (70.7%) indicated that all forms of accountability (administrative-legal and public) should be reflected in educational change management. When we refer to responsibility in education, we have in mind the administrative-institutional and the societal-economic dimensions. The latter encompasses accountability in ensuring educational performance and thus institutional development. In terms of the three forms of accountability (professional, market and financial), 87.8% of respondents opted for professional accountability, 43.9% for financial accountability and a distant 39% for market accountability. Professional accountability leads to ongoing concern for career development and performance in the training of staff employed in the education system. Although respondents give funding accountability an indicator of 43.9%, it plays an extremely important role in providing the other two forms, as funding education is a sustainable investment for the future. From the perspective of the societal-economic dimension, institutional accountability in education determines market-education-market cohesion. In the respondents' opinion, this is supported by connecting the educational offer with the labor market demand (63.4%), developing the cult of education and work (56.1%), adapting the educational offer to the geographical, industrial and social area (53.7%) and developing the cult of profession and professionalism (48.8%). The directions that the interviewees opted for lead to a model centered on the economic sphere of approach to education, in which the market-education-market segment ensures educational change as a response to economic growth and social well-being.

In terms of the application of educational change management, the research has captured the essential elements that converge to support the institutional integrity-transparency nexus. The most common response (80.5% of respondents) was respect for professional ethics, followed at a distance by visibility and access to decision-making (56.1%), respect for fundamental human rights and freedoms (53.7%), working in the spirit of organizational values (34.1%) and good faith execution of legal rules (24.4%). The recognition of professional ethics as a fundamental element of maintaining the integrity-institutional transparency link contributes to the elimination of corruption at any level and of any nature in the education system and to the consolidation of the legal core with that of organizational values. Both visibility and access to the decision-making process and respect for fundamental human rights and freedoms reinforce the need for institutional transparency and social dialogue in education policy decision-making.

Based on these subsidiary hypotheses, the research aimed to identify the priorities of educational change management in order to affirm and increase administrative capacity in the education system. In the opinion of the participants in the study, the priorities specified are in the following order: good administration (41.2%), flexibility to change (35.3%), development of institutional resources (35.3), cohesion between educational provision and the labor market (26.5%).

Founded both on the analysis of the data collected from the respondents and on the foundations of the social science literature, we conclude that the development of the administrative capacity of the national education system is connected to the management of educational change, through the construction of the axis of good management - investment - adaptation - development - cohesion - innovation. Therefore, the application of educational change management is based on the balance between efficiency, accessibility, modernization and adaptation of administrative capacity to the needs of the system. Adapting the national education system to the new challenges of the millennium can be made possible by the common will of education decision-makers, teaching capital and, of course, direct and indirect beneficiaries. Consequently, developing the administrative capacity of the national education system in the context of educational change management is a *sine qua non* for ensuring good governance in education.

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